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Scaling up the SunDial to TRL4: experimentation at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid premises

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1. Introduction

The industrial sector is a significant contributor, accounting for 20% of total greenhouse gas emissions, especially when electricity consumption is not reallocated. However, there is hope for decarbonizing this sector through the utilization of solar heat for industrial processes (SHIP). While flat plate collectors have been predominantly used for industrial solar heat applications, they are limited to temperatures below 80 °C. This poses a challenge since industrial requirements often demand temperatures exceeding 150 °C, necessitating the adoption of concentrating solar collectors. Conventional options like linear Fresnel and parabolic trough collectors can provide solar heat within the 150-300 °C temperature range. Nevertheless, these collectors were initially designed for much higher temperatures, resulting in elevated installation and maintenance costs when employed within this narrower range. The SunDial is an innovative collector for medium-temperature industrial processes that consists of two parallel rows of linear Fresnel collectors mounted on a rotating platform that tracks the Sun. Based on three Spanish patents [1-3], its optical behaviour was previously validated on a small scale [4-5].

In the framework of the H2020 ASTEP project, an experimental facility has been installed at the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) to validate the SunDial technology and the ASTEP balance of plant at a laboratory scale. Within the ASTEP project, two design approaches have been explored: one without mirror tracking, for low latitudes, which reduces costs but also efficiency, and another with mirror tracking for high latitudes, enhancing performance [6-9]. Both configurations were designed, manufactured, installed, and tested, aiming for an output temperature above 150°C for industrial heat applications and a thermal power output of approximately 25 kWth.

The present paper presents the test loop installed at UPM premises and the first results obtained for one of the collectors. The SunDial collector itself is not introduced in this work, as it has already been presented in previous articles [6].

2. The ASTEP system: balance of plant of the test-loop

The ASTEP system consists of a solar concentrator, a phase change material (PCM) thermal storage system and a connection to the industrial heat demand. The selected heat transfer fluid is thermal oil due to the lower zero temperatures at one of the end-user locations which prevent the use of water. The systems for the high and low-latitude locations will be installed in two factories with different heat demands. The heating strategy involves two levels of power and temperature supply to the process, with a total maximum demand of 14 kWth for both end-users.

Previous studies have analysed both series and parallel connections between the SunDial collector and the storage system, with the former proving to be the superior solution [10]. However, the installation commissioned by F2I2 does not include the PCM storage system or the heat exchange to the demand, which is tested at TRL 4 at UPCT premises. The whole ASTEP concept, including both the SunDial and the PCM-based storage system together with the control system, will be implemented and tested in the end-user's premises to achieve TRL 5. In the installation commissioned by F2I2, heat is dissipated by two air coolers, one emulating the thermal storage in charging mode (maximum power 20 kWth) and the other simulating the industrial load (14 kWth). The balance of plant includes:

- A primary pump (MP) to circulate thermal oil through the testing loop.
- A three-way valve to bypass the SunDial (SV), which would be used at end-user sites when the sun is unavailable but and the storage tank is not depleted.
- A recirculation pump (RP) and to keep the temperature at the demand inlet constant.
- A three-way valve (BPV) to keep the temperature and mass flow at the demand inlet constant.
- Two air-coolers to mimic emulate storage (charging mode) and industrial heat demand.

Additionally, each concentrator includes a large recirculation system to maintain a sufficiently high mass flow through the receiver tubes (SP), which are 70 mm in diameter. The SunDial is equipped with a defocus controller that limits the maximum outlet temperature by moving the SunDial azimuthally to defocus the mirrors and reduce the impinging power [11]. The system counts with an expansion tank to equalize the pressure in the circuit due to the thermal oil dilatation. Both SunDials prototypes share the same balance of plant, thus only one of them can be tested at the time. The balance of plant counts with a manifold with manual valves that can be used to isolate the SunDial. Fig. 1 depicts the flow diagram for the test loop installed, along with the layout of the installation, in which the balance of plant is positioned centrally in the two SunDials. A close-up view of the balance of plant is also given.

Fig. 1. Flow diagram for the test loop (top) and layout of the installation, including collectors and BOP (bottom)

3. Current state of the test loop

The construction of the test loop has faced many challenges, leading to important delays. The current situation of the experimental field is the following:

- The balance of plant is operative, where pumps, valves, and sensors are working correctly. However, the insulation was installed more than one year ago, and due to budget constraints, no solid aluminium jacket was installed. With time, the soft aluminium jacket has been broken in some parts and, thus, the insulation wool has been humidified and deteriorated.
- The SunDial designed for low latitudes (with no mirror-tracking) is operating. However, some fine focusing operations are to be accomplished to improve its performance. A couple of mirrors are broken (total 1.5 m²) and they are not as clean as they should. The recirculation pump of Sundial collector has important leakages when operating at full speed and, thus, it is operated only at 5 Hz, which reduces the oil velocity within the receiver below 1 m/s.
- The SunDial for high latitudes (with azimuth and mirrors-tracking) has been installed, but some small misalignments between some mirrors and the receivers are to be solved. As a result, it is not operative yet.

Fig. 2 shows two pictures of both SunDial collectors in their current state.

Fig. 2. Low-latitude SunDial being tested (left) and high-latitude SunDial (right)

4. Preliminary results

This section presents the results of a test carried out on January 31st, where a special methodology was carried out: as the thermal losses in the BOP were too high, the SunDial was operated using only its embedded pump (SP in Fig.1) at 5 Hz, with the main pump (MP) turned off. Less than one hour after the sun's culmination, the MP was turned on and slowly increased its frequency up to 50 Hz. Fig.3 depicts the variation of the temperatures and frequency of the pumps, for the location of sensors and pumps, refer to Fig. 1. It is important to note that, in the low-latitude SunDial, the output temperature sensor is not within the SunDial recirculation loop, but just after its connection to the balance of plant. Therefore, when the MP is off its measurement does not correspond to the real value.

Fig. 3. Pumps frequency (left) and temperatures in the test loop (right) during the experimentation carried out on January 31st

It can be observed that the SP is always at 5 Hz, whereas the MP starts operating after 13:50 with a very low-frequency increase speed due to the PID adjustment implemented during the experiment. As the T7 sensor is positioned at the beginning of the connecting pipe to the BOP, the temperature peak is obtained just after the MP starts, whereas the thermal front takes some time to attain other sensors. The maximum temperature measured by T7 was around 150 °C, whereas thermal losses and piping inertia decreased the temperature of the thermal front down to 120 °C at the entrance of the storage heat exchanger, and 70 °C at the last temperature measured before the re-entrance to the SunDial. As cold oil enters the SunDial, the outlet temperature decreases until a stable temperature above 90 °C is obtained.

From the measurement of mass flows and temperature, thermal losses can be estimated, see Fig. 4:

Fig. 4. Estimated thermal losses during the experimentation carried out on January 31st

The values of thermal losses when the thermal front is passing through the circuit should not be considered. When the estimated losses are stabilized, we can observe thermal losses are significant, around 7 kW when only temperatures below 100 °C are obtained by the SunDial. It is important to note that, although the SunDial outlet temperature sensor is positioned at the beginning of the connecting pipe to the BOP, where thermal losses at the SunDial outlet are negligible, the SunDial inlet temperature sensor is located just after the MP. This results in considerable thermal losses before the oil even enters the SunDial that are not considered. Given that the distance between T6 and the SunDial entrance is similar to the distance between T7 and T1 and, therefore, thermal losses can be estimated to be the same.

Fig. 5 presents the thermal power collected by the SunDial during the experimentation. The figure highlights the following key elements:

- Power: This is the total enthalpy increase per time from T6 to T7.
- Power+estimated losses T6 to entrance: This is the sum of the power and the estimated thermal losses at the entrance, assuming these losses are similar to those between the SunDial outlet and Storage inlet, as seen in Fig. 4.
- Power considering DNI: This is the total power from the mirrors, calculated by multiplying the total mirror surface area (47 m²) by the Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI). It is the reference for the collector efficiency.

- Power considering DHI: This is the power obtained by multiplying the mirror surface area by the DNI and the cosine of the zenith angle. It is equivalent to the direct solar energy impinging to a 47 m² horizontal surface.
- Power considering DI on a 10° tilted plane: This calculation takes into account the DNI, the mirror surface area, and the cosine of the zenith angle adjusted for a 10° tilt. It represents the direct solar energy impinging to a 47 m² surface tilted 10° with the floor, which is the longitudinal tilt of the Fresnel collectors on the SunDial platform.
- Power considering DI on 10° tilted plane: It is the mirror total surface times the DNI times the cosine of the zenith angle minus 10. It is equivalent to the direct solar energy impinging to a 47 m² surface tilted 10° with the floor, which is the longitudinal tilt of the Fresnel collectors on the SunDial platform.

Fig. 5. Estimated power and power reference during the experimentation carried out on January 31st

One can observe that the power collected by the SunDial, after accounting for the estimated thermal losses at the entrance, is between 5 and 7 kW once the thermal front has passed through the circuit. This value is lower than the expected ranges of 10 to 14 kW for this time of the year. However, it should be considered that mirrors have not been cleaned before the test, that two mirrors were broken (therefore the reflecting surface is 45.5 m² and not 47 m²) and that still a final focusing operation is to be done to increase the curvature of mirrors.

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